

TIL O'ZLASHTIRISH JARAYONINI TESTLAR ORQALI BAHOLASH

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Ingliz tili va adabiyoti kafedراسi o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada, til o'zlashtirish jarayonining baholashi borasidagi muammolar, test tizimlarining qay darajada sifatli ekanligi, til o'qitish guruhlarida baholashning tutgan o'rni, test tizimining o'rganuvchilarga ta'siri, xalqaro e'tirof etilgan til baholash tizimlari va ularning tuzilishi haqida so'z yuritiladi

Kalit so'zlar: Baholar, tizim mahsuldorligi, test tizimi, bir tilli, standard test baholash tizimi.

WASHBACK IN LANGUAGE ASSESSMENT

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Annotation: This article investigates issues in the field of language testing, the efficiency of testing systems, the role of testing system in language learning classes, the impact of washback on language learners, globally recognized test systems and their construction.

Key words: Assessment, systematic efficiency, testing system, monolingual, standardized language testing.

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Аннотация: В этой статье исследуются вопросы в области языкового тестирования, эффективность систем тестирования, роль системы тестирования в занятиях по изучению языка, влияние обратной связи на изучающих язык, всемирно признанные системы тестирования и их построение.

Ключевые слова: оценивание, систематическая эффективность, система тестирования, одноязычное, стандартизированное языковое тестирование.

In the field of education, assessment is the vital process which helps to reinforce the acquisition level of a certain subject. Furthermore, efficient assessing students' knowledge can motivate student's inner temptation to learn more and wisely. Up to now, there have been many projects in the area of education, especially in the branch of evaluating learner's ability on a certain field. Research into washback can be traced back to the early 1980s, when the influence of tests on teaching and learning was first seen as a potential source of bias due to the accountability of test feedback loops. As the results of tests became more important to students (gatekeepers to future prospects), teachers (evaluation), schools (funding), and states (lawsuits), test preparation as a function of teaching became essential. Tests were made to be economical, using multiple-choice questions and focusing on psychometric validity, but perhaps not measuring more complex abilities. Schools and teachers were accountable for student test performance, and thus focused on the skills and outcomes that the tests measured. Given the dynamic interaction between testing and education, the term systematic validity was used to refer to the ways in which a test leads to changes in instruction intended to develop cognitive skills that are being measured by a test.[1]

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Furthermore, assessing students' ability plays a vital role in teaching field. To be more specific, motivation in language teaching helps to stimulate students desire to study more. If the testing system is implemented efficiently, the acquisition process can be accelerated considerably. However, there is another side of testing system which sometimes demotivates their intention of studying. Because, when a student cannot get the expected result, they may lose their temptation to study further.

As we above mentioned, a number of researches have been done concerning the effect of washback on learners and their acquisition level. It is well known fact that washback effects on individuals differently and various degrees. Effects may be superficial, indirect, and unpredictable due to individual differences in the way that learning is mediated by teachers, textbook writers, and publishers [2]. It can be seen from this statement that teachers are not supposed to expect the same reaction or result by implementing test system in educational process. This is because, individual differences do not allow to get expected result. Recently, different questions about the impact of tests are being asked. However, individual differences are the only aspect to deal with. The validity of current test materials and their proper usage have to be concerned also. Work from the field of World Englishes has called into question the validity of tests in light of the use of English as an "international" language—specifically the extent to which current tests and test design practices represent the way English is now used in the global context [3]. Nowadays, there a number of standardized official tests such as Test of English for International Communication (TOEIC), Test of English as a Foreign Language (TOEFL), and International English Language Testing System (IELTS) and they are considered as standard tools in the wider learning community. However, the wider usage of those tests over the world may raise questions about their difficulty and the stress they may put on learners. The increasing weight of these tools in education raised questions about the impact of such tests on teaching and learning, with suggestions that language skills were suffering due to the impact of tests. Besides that, criteria designation is considered as crucial as other

factors. This is because, these tests are designed to reveal students' knowledge and do not involve other functions.

Among current test types, In standardized language testing, the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) provides the best example of a clear use of standards. The CEFR is used throughout the world as the clarity of the descriptions of levels in the framework help to alleviate some of the problems associated with testing constructs. However, the essential construct of EIL is not a consideration in the CEFR. The “can do” statements indicate that proficient users are responsible for producing L1-level language, without consideration of the competence of interlocutors. This is because the expectation is that the interlocutor is an L1 user of English. However, as the majority of English users are EIL users, while those L1 English norms are the boundaries in which shades of meaning are to be contained, there needs to be a cooperative negotiation between communicators in establishing understanding. In addition, International English language testing system (IELTS) is being widely used over the world and accepted by both teachers and student more alternative testing system. This testing includes nearly all skills and help to reveal learners' language acquisition. The construction of that type is somehow similar to other test systems but has enough differences such as the type of writing and other skill materials.

Thus, testing in the TEIL context takes a “plurilithic” view of English that rejects the monolithic “L1-speaker” view of language. It embraces the reality that English is not learned monolingually, but rather bi- or multilingually [3]. The particular construct that TEIL provokes is the relationship between competence and performance. By not conforming to L1 speaker norms, L2 users of EIL are assessed as incompetent. Regarding learning achievement of language in use, any nonconformity is also seen as incompetent. However, research in TEIL has made it clear that what may be assessed as “incompetence” in no way impedes EIL users from performing competently in communication [3]. Looking at the statements above, we can conclude that all aspects

should be taken into consideration in order to get the expected result from washback in learning sphere.

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